

HUMAN RIGHTS

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Ensuring human rights is our main goal.

Annotation: This article examines a declaration known to all as the “Universal Declaration of Human Rights”, the works have been done to ensure human rights and freedoms in Uzbekistan. The purpose of this article is to provide precise information about human rights in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key concepts: UDHR - Universal Declaration of Human Rights, UN – United Nations, the National Center for Human Rights of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Cabinet of Ministers, OSCE – Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe, UNESCO, UNICEF, Oliy Majlis

Human rights are rights we have simply because we exist as human beings - they are not granted by any state. These universal rights are inherent to us all, regardless of nationality, sex, national or ethnic origin, color, religion, language, or any other status. They range from the most fundamental - the right to life - to those that make life worth living, such as the rights to food, education, work, health, and liberty.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1948, was the first legal document to set out the fundamental human rights to be universally protected. The UDHR, which turned 70 in 2018, continues to be the foundation of all international human rights law. Its 30 articles provide the principles and building blocks of current and future human rights conventions, treaties and other legal instruments.

Of course, ensuring human rights is main goal for every country, including Uzbekistan too.

The greatest goal of Uzbekistan, moving forward along the path of independent democracy, is significant, first of all, in carrying out reforms in the interests of our people. These aspects are also enshrined in our Constitution. In particular, Article 13 of Chapter II of the Constitution states: “Democracy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on universal human principles, according to which a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inalienable rights are the highest values.

The National Center for Human Rights of the Republic of Uzbekistan, working in coordination with the work to ensure human rights and freedoms in our country, is committed to the implementation of such noble deeds. On October 31 this year, the Center turns 26 years old. Over the past period, the Center has been working on developing a strategy for developing a major national action plan, implementing the Constitution, laws and generally recognized norms of international human rights law, preparing national reports. On the observance and protection of these rights, advising state authorities and administration, as well as human rights public associations, as well as the implementation of various activities to promote and protect human rights.

In a short historical period, a legal framework has been created in Uzbekistan for the formation of national statehood. Our country, like all developed legal states, is divided into three branches of power: legislative, executive and judicial. A strong economy based on free market relations was created in order to quickly move from a strong rule of law to a civil society on the path to prosperity. Thus, our country has become a full and equal subject of international law. Of course, all this was achieved thanks to the dedication, initiative and leadership of President Islam Karimov. United Nations Office for the Promotion of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms United Nations 1996 Decree of 31 October 2006 established the National Center for Human Rights of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The decree clearly defines the goals and main tasks of the National Center for Human Rights.

The organizational and legal basis of the National Center is the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated November 13, 1996 "On the establishment of the National Center for Human Rights of the Republic of Uzbekistan". This decision approved the Regulations on the National Center of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Human Rights and the structure of the National Center. The National Center for Human Rights of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a body for analysis, interpretation and coordination of the activities of state bodies. In other words, this body coordinates the activities of state administration bodies in the field of human rights, develops a national work plan in the field of human rights, prepares national reports of Uzbekistan on human rights, and for civil servants, the protection of human rights and the protection of human rights. It can be said that the main goal of the Center is the development and implementation of a comprehensive program for the protection of human rights and freedoms, the National Action Plan for Human Rights through a comprehensive solution of these fundamental tasks.

At the same time, it is worth noting the international cooperation of the National Center. In particular, the United Nations Development Program in Uzbekistan, the OSCE Project Coordinator in Uzbekistan, the International Labor Organization, the Delegation of the European Union in Uzbekistan, UNESCO, UNICEF and other international organizations in our country. In cooperation with international partners, various projects are being implemented in our country aimed at further strengthening, protecting and promoting human rights and freedoms. At present, the information and legal department of the Center has the only specialized public library on human rights in Central Asia. The library consists of books, magazines and other literature published in Uzbek and foreign languages, and has a book fund of more than 5,000 titles on human rights. The Center has published more than 150 collections, books and other literature on human rights in the state language in thousands of copies.

Formation of national human rights institutions in Uzbekistan as part of the process of reform and modernization of the country, democratic reforms have been

carried out in all spheres of the state and society. In particular, the Decree of the President of May 1, 2008 “On the Program of events dedicated to the 60th anniversary of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights” is an important step in strengthening the legal status of national human rights institutions in Uzbekistan. The presidential decree provides for further organizational and legal improvement of the human rights protection system, as well as state support for national human rights institutions, strengthening the material and technical base, the National Center for Human Rights and the National Institute for Human Rights. it is planned to take comprehensive measures to create favorable conditions.

The adopted normative documents to support the activities of national human rights institutions, the improvement of the legal framework of national institutions in order to bring them into line with international standards testify to Uzbekistan's commitment to democratic reforms.

Currently, he is the Authorized Person of the Oliy Majlis for Human Rights (Ombudsman), one of the national human rights institutions operating in the country, the Institute for Monitoring Legislation in Action under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the National Center. As a result of the efforts of these organizations, a solid legal framework for the protection of human rights has been created in our country. During the years of independence, constitutional laws, codes and other laws on the protection of fundamental human rights and freedoms have been adopted and are being implemented. “On Guarantees of the Rights of the Child”, “On Combating Human Trafficking”, “On the Social Protection of the Disabled in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, “On Guarantees of Human Rights and the Activities of Non-Governmental Organizations” The foundation is being laid for improving the legal framework for protection.

At the same time, in addition to the above institutions, the Center for the Democratization and Liberalization of the Judiciary under the Supreme Court, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Justice and the judiciary of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs has effective human rights divisions and departments.

In Uzbekistan, the supremacy of generally recognized principles and norms of international law is recognized on a constitutional basis. To date, our country has ratified more than 70 international human rights treaties, in particular 10 binding international human rights treaties adopted by the United Nations, and consistently fulfills its international obligations.

In short, demonstrating Uzbekistan's commitment to democratic reforms, as well as protecting and promoting human rights, are among its top priorities in an era of great change and renewal in our country. The National Center for Human Rights of the Republic of Uzbekistan occupies a unique place among the existing national institutions in our society.

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